

The effect of structural connectome estimation in modelling whole-brain functional dynamics

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Introduction

The brain's structure-function relationship is an important open problem in neuroscience, with many whole-brain models developed to study how functional dynamics derive from the anatomical organisation[1-3]. Significant developments on ensemble neural masses (or finer neural fields) aim to increase accuracy of such models[4]. However, a backbone of these models, the map of structural connections, typically estimated from diffusion MRI data, has received less attention. How this map is estimated and processed can lead to less or more faithful representations of true biophysical features of brain's connectivity; e.g., distributions of connection strengths and path lengths[5-7]. Here, we use a modular framework to explore the influence of such features in whole-brain models of functional dynamics. We show that they can have significant effects on modelling performance, when comparing forward predictions with empirical data.

Methods

We built whole-brain neuronal models, as networks of regional neural mass models linked through a structural connectome (Fig. 1). Using data from the Human Connectome Project[6], we could estimate subject-specific connectomes from diffusion MRI tractography, use them in the model and compare modelled functional connectivity (FC) to the FC measured for the same subject through resting-state functional MRI. That way we directly assessed the effect of several choices in building structural connectomes on the accuracy of in-silico predictions of the individual FC.

We modelled local node dynamics as a combination of the mean-field neural mass model of[4] with the balloon-Windkessel model governing the haemodynamic response. We subsequently followed the approach of[9], linearising around a stable fixed point to find the Jacobian matrix. Using this to numerically solve a Lyapunov equation gave the covariances of the 2 neuronal and 4 haemodynamic variables. Extracting the correlations of the blood-oxygen-level-dependent response yielded a synthetic FC matrix, which we compared to the corresponding empirical FC using Pearson's correlation of vectorised connectivity matrices.

We explored the effect of 3 main features in building a structural connectome on the performance of our functional network model: *a) Tractography seeding*, as this has a significant effect in the represented distributions of connectivity weights[5]. We performed probabilistic tractography with 2 strategies: seeds placed on the surface of the white matter/ grey matter

boundary (C_1); and whole-brain seeds (C_2). *b) Cortical parcellation*. We estimated dense structural connectomes (60K² cortical surface vertices), which were then parcellated with a coarse (Desikan-Killiany, 68 nodes), intermediate (Destrieux, 148 nodes), or fine (Glasser, 360 nodes) atlas. *c) Normalisation*. Parcellated structural matrices were normalised/scaled in various ways (logarithmic and/or fractional scaling, constant row-sum or symmetric normalisation[10]).

Results

Fig. 2A suggests symmetric normalisation works better, across seeding strategies, for coarser parcellations, and equally well to row normalisation for finer parcellations. The model also performed better with unscaled connection weights than log-scaled weights. Next, we compared the effects of fractional scaling on both unscaled and log-scaled matrices (Fig. 2B) and did not find a significant improvement. Hence, we kept unscaled and symmetrically normalised connectivity matrices to do a larger comparison between seeding strategies for both single-hemisphere and whole-brain data (Fig. 2C). In summary, whole-brain seeding with unscaled weights and symmetric normalisation worked better for predicting individual FC using our whole-brain model of network dynamics.

Conclusion

Our results suggest high sensitivity (up to 50% change) of modelling performance to the structural connectome estimation parameters. Hence there is a need for more systematic criteria to determine how these choices are made and optimised.

Figure 1: Modelling whole-brain functional dynamics and connectivity. (A) Schematic illustrating the pipeline. Structural connectivity is obtained by applying one of two tractography strategies to diffusion MRI data, which is parcellated, scaled and normalised to obtain a connectivity matrix C for a neural mass model. The mathematical model combines this matrix with neural dynamics and haemodynamics to generate a network differential equation, which is linearised in a vicinity of a fixed point to obtain a synthetic resting state functional connectivity matrix. By comparing this to empirical BOLD-fMRI data, we can evaluate the performance of different choices made in the pipeline. (B) Examples of data used in this study. The top row shows data parcellated using the Desikan-Killiany atlas (68 nodes), while the bottom row was parcellated with the Glasser atlas (360 nodes).

Figure 2: Connectome estimation and post-processing choices cause significant differences in model performance. Violin plots depict distributions across 40 HCP subjects. **(A-B)** Comparing the effects of scaling and normalisation type on model performance for whole-brain data. **(A)** Row normalisation and logarithmic scaling are evaluated against symmetric normalisation. **(B)** Evaluation of fractional scaling (on unscaled and log-scaled connectivity matrices). **(C)** Having determined the optimal scaling and normalisation, we compare the effects of seeding strategy on both whole-brain and single-hemisphere data. *Logarithmic scaling:* the value of each entry C_{ij} is replaced by $\log_{10}(1 + C_{ij})$. *Fractional scaling:* the final values are $C_{ij} / \sum_k (C_{ik} + C_{kj})$, i.e. a connection between two nodes is weighted as a fraction of all connections involving those parcels. *Symmetric normalisation:* an iterative procedure in which the matrix symmetry is preserved by simultaneously scaling the matrix by its row and column sums.

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